

MUSLIM WOMENS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN AROUND VELLORE DISTRICT -A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

T.E.IMTHIYAZ ISMAIL

Ph.D. Research Scholar (Full-Time)

P.G. Research Department of History

C. Abdul Hakeem College (Autonomous) Melvisharam

Affiliated By Thiruvalluvar University

Serkkadu Vellore Tamil Nadu India.

&

Dr .A .ABDUL JAMEEL

Assistant Professor Research Guide & Supervisor

P.G. Research Department of History

C. Abdul Hakeem College (Autonomous) Melvisharam

Affiliated By Thiruvalluvar University

Serkkadu Vellore Tamil Nadu India.

Abstract

The paper is dealing on access to education of Muslims in general and Muslim women in particular. The earlier shape of centers for importing religions education to the girl was more or less medieval. There used to be in every locality a pious lady who was assigned the duty of teaching the Quran and explaining the rudimentary Knowledge of religion. Newer was a girl ever taught how to write in rare cases at the behest of the parents a girl was instructed as to how a pen is to be held. The only occasion for a girl to hold a pen and sign her name was in the marriage register. Though she was not taught the method of writing she was made conversant with the written form and every girl was made to commit to memory the first portion of the Quran as it was essential for saying prayers. Some efforts were taken by the Ulema of the Vellore district to propagate education among women. Separate Makatib were established in every locally. They were attached to the mosques and maintained by the jamats. They provided fundamental knowledge of Urdu, Arabic and the Quran the Muslim girls of the Vellore district received education in these Makatib.

Keywords;

Ulema.Makatib.Jamats.Ramzon.Haj.Jamia Darussalaam.Quran.Hadith.Madrassa-I-Niswan.Fumd-Talim-Niswan.Quran.Anjuman-E-Ansaru.

Introduction

Very little effort was taken to provide higher education to them. Being conservatives the parents as well as the community were satisfied when their daughters acquired basic knowledge of religion so that they could perform from religious duties such as saying prayers reciting the Quran fasting month of Ramzon and performing Haj. The Vaniyambadi Muslim Were the pioneers of the Muslim Education in Vellore district. They turned their attention to Female education and called for a meeting of important leaders of the town on March 11.1910 to find out ways and means of Established a girl's School. They decided to raise a Fumd-Talim-Niswan fund Hazarath Maulana Muhammad Abdur Rahim Sahib popularly known as Bade Hazarath took the initiative in this respect. He was encouraged and support by Krishnagiri Muhammad Abdullah Sahib, Abdul Hameed Sahib and Rabgoon Hakeem Abdul Hameed sahib,¹

Maulana Fazalullah sahib. Who later becomes the First principle of Jamia Darussalaam. Omerbad delivered many inspiring speeches on the importance of Women's education quoting from the Quran and Hadith. The generous Muslim merchant of Vaniyambadi responded positively to these appeals and come forward with donations for this noble cause. As a result Madrasa-I-Niswan was established in 1911A.D. with 55 girls on the rolls. It developed into a reputed and standard school in Vellore district under the stewardship of Moulana Muhammad Abdul Majeed Khan sahib. A modified version of Darse Nizami was prescribed as syllabus. It proved a trendsetter.²

Only students less than seven years allowed coming by walk for all others and the staff member's bullock carts and vans are sent to their houses to fetch them to school. In evening they have to return in the same carts and vans students are not charged for transport. Neither admission fee nor tuition fee is collected. More than 200 students are being provided mid-day meals since 1960. Poor girls who come from far off places and those local students whose parents have meager economic means are provided free boarding and lodging. In course of time many more institutions sprang up to provide opportunities for female education.

PIONEER GIRLS MUSLIM EDUCATIONAL SOCIETIES

The Muslim of Vellore District was in favors of women's education. They established schools for girls through their societies from elementary level to higher secondary level and collegiate level. Due to their sound financial position they were liberally assisting both secular and religious educational institutions. Renewed Educational societies such as Vaniyambadi Muslim society The Ambur Muslim educational society and the Melvisharam Educational Society run reputed elementary school and high schools and even colleges for girls. However women's education in Vellore District was not promising due to various reasons. But the awakening among the Muslim community in the beginning of the Twentieth Century and the

Changing attitude of the British Government and the solid steps taken by free Indian Government paved way for the development of Muslim women's education. The Muslim parents have now realized the necessity of secular religions education to their daughters.⁴

VELLORE REGION

Muslim is living in considerable number in Vellore District. Except a few most of the Muslims are below the poverty line though there are two Municipal girls schools and few schools run by the private managements for girls the turnout of Muslim children in general and Muslim girls in particular is very low. This is because majorly of the Muslim who is by poverty keep their children at home to help them in their house hold works. Municipal Muslim Girls School Ramanaikan papayam (Rahmathpala.Vellore) was established in 1923 by local Muslim organized in the same year by the Government. In early years the strength of the school was just fifty and classes from one to fifth standards were handled by three teachers including Tamil language teachers the school adopts syllabus prescribed by the Tamil Nadu Government

Municipal Muslim Girl's Primary School in Saidapet by Vellore with Urdu medium was initiated by the Muslim of Vellore before 1930 and was recognized by the state Government in 1939. Student is taught in Mathematics. Science. Urdu. History. Geography and Tamil. There are three Urdu teachers and one Tamil teacher and Muslim children of surrounding area are largely benefited by this institution. Urdu Aided Girls Middle School in Baqiyyath Street enjoys the privileged student strength of 290 girls. Subject is taught as per the state Government syllabus in Urdu medium along with religions instruction (Recitation of the Quran and Hades). Parents of the girls in this locality are very conservative and do not send their daughters for higher studies this school established in 1974 as a primary school was upgraded as Middle school,⁵

ARCOT REGION

There is only Muslim Girls educational institution is functioning in Arcot to provide education Muslim girls Madras-E-Yomia. Arcot was started in the year 1926. It was an orphanage for Muslim boys and girls with an endowment by the Arcot Nawab with jagirs to meet the expenses and salary of the teacher in the beginning. It functional in a building but later on shifted to the building donated by the prince of Arcot. Muslim girls from Arcot and its suburbs had their primary education there in 1960. It was brought under the control of Arcot Municipally and its name was changed as Municipal Girls' Elementary school even now it is functioning with the endowment created by the prince of Arcot. Janab T. Muhammad Rizwanullah. MA. is the Headmaster of the school with two more staff

MELVISHARAM REGIO

Mevisharam is a Town thickly populated with Muslim the natives are highly religions and venerate Islam more than anything else for the past 300 years the Town's women are studying the Quran and the Muslim girls are trained in religions education was given to children in their own house and mosques that had come up town. In the second half of the Twentieth century Muslim of this Town felt the growing need of education for women and established schools to give both secular and religious education.

Madrassa-A-Niswan a religious institution is managed by Anjuman-E-Ansaru Islam and the institution was established in 1941. The present president of the society is Janab Malak Muhammad Hashim Sahib and Secretary is Malak Akbar Hussain sahib the objective of this Niswan to provide religions education to the Muslim girls of the Town in the blazing light of the Quran and Hades. At present janab Shakra saheba is headmaster and 500 students are on rolls and 27 teachers are working in the school thought the madrasa is registered institution the Management is not receiving any grant from the Government. Salary for the teachers is met by the management by collecting donations from the well wishers and other stakeholders.

GUDIYATTAM REGION

Gudiyattam is a Taluk headquarters and a cosmopolitan Town. Around 75% of the Muslim are Beedi workers and living under poverty line. Girls of these families are not sent to schools and they are forced to assist their parents in rolling Beedis. Therefore the number of school going girls very low when compared to other towns. Municipal Girls primary school Dharnampet by Gudiyattam came in to existence in 1935 and recognized by the British Government in 1940. The student strength is 150 and they are guided by five trained teachers After passing out their elementary education only few students join High schools rest of the students discounts their studies because of their poverty and at present this school is managed town's municipally.⁶

AMBUR REGION

Ambur a famous historical Town where the British and French fought for their supremacy in 1751 is known for its educational institutions managed by Hindus Muslim and Christians. From primary level to higher secondary level there are schools for Muslim girls. Habibia Aided Primary school. Ambur was established by famous Habiba Trust of Ambur to felicitate women's education in 1968 had obtained Government recognition. The school is importing instruction from 358 students and ten teaching staff and two non-teaching staff. The two-Floored building of the school has come up in area 3600 square feet.

Ishaatul Hasanath Aided Girls primary school Ambur was started in 1940 wearing its first name after the town affluent chia faintly name after them as Chia Madrasa it was renamed as Ishaatul Hasnath Aided Girls primary school in 1943. The school has earned good reputation as it insists on discipline sincerity and hard work.

MMES WOMES'S ARTS AND SCIENCES COLLEGE

Melvisharam Muslim educational society was 2007 start MMES College in women in melvisharan under the self-financing pattern Affiliation to Thiruvalluvar University. The Society has taken extensive interest and got Tamil Nadu Government higher education department approval. The college committee was formed in which Alijanab. Alhaj S. Ziauddin Ahmed Sahib is the Chairman Alhaj Matheen Sahib was first corresponded of this college.

Placement Cell & Campus Interview:-

The Placement cell is one of the prime sectors in M.M.E.S College, set for the career development of our students.

Objectives:-

To organize campus interviews for final year students with industries and business houses of reputation from all over India. To prepare students to face campus interviews by giving them training in Aptitude tests, Group Discussions and preparing them for technical and HR interviews through professional trainers.⁷

MMES has an Active Placement Cell with a full time Placement Officer to arrange for:

- Career Development Programmers
- Off-Campus interviews
- Industrial Visits
- To arrange for the final semester projects by the students

State Initiatives/ Measures

Government of India has introduced several policies and programmers to upgrade the existing situation of Muslim women in particular and Muslims in general. Indian state also establishes certain commission and committee to implement monitor and examine the policies related to Muslim Community. Article 46 of the Constitution states that, "The State shall promote, with special care, the education and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people, and, in particular of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of social exploitation." Similarly, Articles 30 (1) provides for the rights of the Minorities to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice. National Policy on Education (NPE) adopted the concept of national system of education, implying that up to a certain level all students irrespective of caste, creed, language or Gender has access to education of comparable quality.

CONCLUSI

Therefore, it can be observed that to include Vellore Muslim women in modern educational attainment, State should connect with convent school, to enroll Muslim women on zero fee bases in highly backward Muslim women's in Vellore district concentrated areas and rest of the burden sponsor by the State as most of the Muslim girls' and boys' join madrasas. curriculum of madrasa education is need to be comprehend and must be equal in proportion of modern educational subjects and also include Some creative or artistic subject for future reference to self-worth. Socio economic backwardness indicator thereof should be organized properly and considered before framing educational policy or providing subsidy, rather than basing it on religion. This would enhance the overall development effort currently gaining momentum in the country. Challenges are going to remain to forthwith development and progress in women condition. Indicators which used to assess the status, policy must be centered to achieve the improvements in indicators respectively.

REFERENCE

1. Aainay vaniyambadi.op.cit.p.98
2. Madras-E-Ni-swan Calender.Melvisharam; 1957.p.2.
3. Golden jubilee Souvenir; Madras-E-Mazharul Uloom High School Ambur; Muslim educational society.1995.p.8
4. Charters Molon, A Book of the south India. London.1926.p.198.
5. Madrasa-E-Niswan Vaniyambadi. A Brochure. (Urdu) p.2.
6. Hakeem Abdul Hameed. Educational survey Report on Muslim Managed Schools and Colleges in India. New Delhi. 1983. P.68.
7. Report of education Commission. 1964-1966; Education and National Development New Delhi.1966,p,83
8. R.C.No.131, D.E.O. Vellore District.26 April 1923.
9. R.C,No.188/26.Department of School education. Chennai.
10. Abdul Latheef. k.Sheher visharam Tarik-ke-Aaine May.Vellore.1992.p.33.